

Development of Management Education System in India

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Abstract

The discipline of management / business education has emerged, in the past 50 years, as one of the notable and nearly about more than 120 universalities, 8 IIMs and a number of private institutions are offering a wide variety of degrees at Masters level and Doctoral level as well as Diploma programmes. However, the fastest growth has been at the masters level particularly MBA, which is regarded as an essential professional preparation for managers, both in public and private sectors. Relevance of management education has become more imperative, only during post liberalisation and this has marked a change in the way management education is perceived in India. It is often said that management education in India has attained a stage of maturity but this is qualified to mean that theoretical knowledge and training imparted is on par with many other well-known counterpart institutions in the western world. Presently the postgraduate management programmes of study consist of two-year full time MBA programmes, and part-time 3-year duration. Some universities have even started a bachelors degree programme like BBM, BBA etc. In this direction, management education must be made 'Mass Education' rather than the 'Class Education' and that too, without compromising on quality. Therefore, management institutes must strive to develop global manager of proper knowledge, attitude, skill, insight and foresight to meet the challenges of 21st century.

Key Words: Education, Talent, Quality, Management, Global.

Introduction

Management education in the country can roughly be divided into four groups. At the top are the reputed institutes and some university departments which have maintained the high quality of their education. The second category institutes are those started by industrial houses, which offer some surety of a job after the course. The third are university departments which have not been able to impart quality education but can provide jobs in regional industrial groups and the fourth are those institutes which have neither the advantage of low fees of a university nor the backing of an industrial house. In recent times, a number of academics, retired people, politicians and others have started such institutes which remain essentially money making devices. Managers, to be globally competitive, require the new skills apart from those already being taught. These are: Information Management and Information Technology Management skill, Decision- making Skill in very dynamic environment, H.R.D Skill, Innovation/ Creativity, Service Sector Management Skills, Time Management Skills, Stress Management Skills, Environment Management Skills, Entrepreneurship Skills, Customers Services Management Skills and Management schools have to develop these skills among students.

Management Education Abroad

The standard period for an international full time MBA in the US is two years. Schools like Wharton, Harvard and Stanford cost approximately US\$34,000 for tuition per annum. In Europe, London Business School offers a two-year programme, whereas IMD, INSEAD, Canfield,

Warwick and other leading institutes programmes are of one year. In Europe, the annual cost of an MBA can be as little as US\$9000 or as much as US\$42,000 for tuition, with books and living expenses a further cost. However, financial aid opportunities also exist that can make the most expensive programmes affordable. Scholarships are offered too by a variety of organizations and many local banks offer low start loans during the period of study. Many companies pay back the tuition fees of an MBA qualification in the form of a "sign on" bonus.

Part-time and distance learning MBA study are also serious alternatives. Over 35,000 people are now using distance learning for an MBA or similar diploma with institutions outside the US and a further 75,000 people are using US institutions. An estimated 600,000 people are studying part-time. This approach is popular because it avoids the need to leave the employment during the study period, and allows the learner to live at home. For those not seeking an international experience, this is a sensible option.

Some Challenges

The real challenge before the management education is that the existing management education system has been patterned on certain western models, particularly USA and has therefore fallen short of expectations to meet several priority sectors in the country like agriculture, health, public distribution system, small business, government and semi-government undertakings etc. Any review of our management education inevitably leads to the question of its relevance to the community needs in all sectors. It is no secret that most of the output of

MBA's are absorbed by the western-oriented private and public sectors leaving high and dry other sectors which are in real need of management.

Though the business practices are rapidly changing with the advent of IT, management education has not kept pace with these changes. The curricula in most business schools are still decades old and are not market driven. Though some of the B-schools have included some IT courses and courses in change management, technology management, innovation management, knowledge management; these are piecemeal approaches and students fail to appreciate the importance of these courses in wider business situations. The defect may also be in teaching methodologies adopted in these schools. Most of the faculty members have no industrial experience and they just provide a theoretical framework for most of the management concepts and fail to bring the relevance and usage of these concepts in rapidly evolving business scenario.

The gap between management education and practices seems to be widening due to inherent problems in implementing some of the principles of management taught in B-school. Also, there is a wide difference between actual business situation and what one learns through case simulation method in the class. Today's management requires more of on-the-feet thinking rather than working out pros and cons of a given situation as reflected in a well-structured case, which takes a lot of time and causes delay in decision-making. There are also inherent contradictions in some of the management principles taught which leave room for ambiguity and doubt.

The cultural and religious aspects of the Indian society also has become a great problem to the management technology. A vast majority of our population is caught up in a vicious circle of poverty, unemployment, religious, linguistic and regional dogmas. Caste system has divided the country into innumerable groups and has prevented social mobility. There is an acute shortage of entrepreneurial skill. The management education has to shake off these inhibitions and turnout a modern person with a new set of attitudes, values and work ethics that are so essential for successful management of the economy.

It is interesting to note that even though most syllabi state that in addition to lectures the courses will be conducted through case methods, role plays, simulation games, etc., in reality the traditional lecture method dominates the management education scene, and case method or other student-involving methodologies usually play a marginal role, except in a few institutions which are explicitly committed to such methodologies.

The overwhelming view is that the quality of faculty is going down as more and more institutes mushrooming with the aim of making money rather than enhancing the quality of education. Similarly, there is a decline in the quality of students, as the sole aim of B-schools has become money-making

Some subjects like organisational behaviour and human resources are difficult to teach, they can only be discussed or learnt through practical experience. It is also felt that like engineering and medical streams, a BBA degree could be of great relevance to those who want to do MBA. There should be no compulsory age and work experience limits for students.

Some Suggestions

In the light of the pitfalls found with the management education system prevailing in India, the paper has tried to recommend the following broad suggestions.

1. Planning for management education has not so far been related to manpower needs. It should be based on specific, authentic data and the national technical manpower system should therefore provide in each plan, realistic estimates of managerial manpower needed for different sectors and at different levels.
2. Management education institutions should be enabled to respond effectively to emerging managerial manpower-needs by diversifying their courses and training programmes to suit different sectors of economic development, as well as fulfill their professional and social objectives.
3. The criticism that the present management education is urban oriented and biased in favour of corporate sectors and that it has fallen short of expectations to meet several priority sectors like agriculture, health, rural and small industries should be met by positive action. This should result in re-statement of the objectives, restructuring the courses and by creating conditions for preparing managers suitable for non-traditional sectors and for self-employment and entrepreneurship.
4. Admission procedures and admission tests should be established to conform to certain standards, so as to ensure quality of students admitted to a variety of courses. Towards, this end, an admission test is conducted at national level.
5. Curricula and courses of study should be upgraded, unitized and made in modular form and also relevant to Indian context. Teaching materials, case studies, audio-visual aids should be developed based on Indian experience and dependence on foreign case studies should be reduced. The content of the curriculum should be such that there is similarity between the

rationality that is taught in the classroom and the ground reality, which a student has to actually face. Projects assigned should be more practical and students should go back to the same organisations to study various departments like HR, finance and marketing, in order to get a holistic understanding.

6. Faculty development should be one of the key areas of action so as to induct into the academic system bright young persons with academic qualifications in management, in order to make management education system self-reliant. Opportunities should be made available for existing staff to acquire advanced training and qualifications in management through provisions of fellowships for advanced study and training.
7. Faculty development programmes, similar to the FIP of the universities and QIP for technical institutions should be initiated in a phased and planned manner so as to update the qualifications and competence of existing faculty.
8. The system should become self-reliant with regard to faculty. The minimum core faculty needed should be available in every department / institute and the present practice on relying mostly on guest faculty only has to be changed, if proper standards are to be maintained.
9. Management school-industry interface and linkages should be strengthened along organised plans, in all aspects such as curriculum development, case studies, exchange of personnel, guest faculty and sharing of resources, project work and placement of graduates etc.
10. There should be free movement of faculty between schools and industry, so as to enrich both the systems through better sharing of real experiences and expertise.
11. The quality of management education in some of the newer schools, particularly those coming under the university system has to be upgraded. The University Grants Commission should recognize the importance of management education and provide stronger support to these new departments in universities.
12. Indian literature in the field of management is very limited. Research in the field of management has not grown the way one would like to see. In fact, If management education has to become more relevant and effective, it has to be supported by research into the problems and issues of administration of Indian organizations.

Conclusion

Future careers in management field would be Knowledge based, information intensive, highly mobile across the world, highly rewarding and On a

fast track. In this direction, management education must be made '**Mass Education**' rather than the '**Class Education**' and that too, without compromising on quality. Therefore, management institutes must strive to develop global manager of proper knowledge, attitude, skill, insight and foresight to meet the challenges of 21st century. **Dr. Laura Tyson of London Business School** has accepted the importance of India's role in developing a well networked management curriculum. Expansion of management education in the post-independence era is unprecedented in the educational history of the country. However in spite of this significant development, a lot more has to be accomplished in respect of increasing its coverage and enhancing its accessibility to various categories of people because there still exists a wide gap between the demand and supply of professionally competent people in the country and this gap is increasing year after year with increasing industrial and business activity. The solution to this problem lies in providing facilities for management education and training which alone can develop professionally competent generations suitable for business, industry and public administration.

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